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Annotation: this article covers the life and scientific work of the great scientist and statesman, a bright representative of the Timurid dynasty, the great thinker Mirzo Ulugbek, whose name is inscribed in gilded letters on the pages of World Science. His outstanding contribution to the development of astronomy, mathematics, geometry, geography and a number of other sciences, the accuracy of the calculations he carried out in the Middle Ages, has still left the people of modern science lol.

Keywords: Temurians, scientific heritage, astronomy, mathematics, historian, geographer, Observatory, madrasa, Movaraunnahr.

The 14th – 15th century thinker who entered World Science with the definition of the second renaissance of the East-he, among the allomas, was the Timurid ruler Mirzo Ulugbek. The focus on science, art in Amir Temur can also be seen in his children and grandchildren. At the beginning of the 15th century, the Movarounnahr throne in Samarkand was ruled by The King and scholar Mirzo Ulugbek (1409-1449). During this period, Samarkand became a major political, Scientific, Cultural Center. As a scholar, educator, ulughbek paid great attention to science and tried to concentrate major scientists in Samarkand. He built many madrasas in Samarkand, Bukhara, Gijduvan. Mirzo Ulugbek also became a patron of Science in conjunction with state affairs¹.

The scientific heritage of the great thinker and the study of state activities are of great interest. Many scientific works and studies in this regard have been carried out by scientists from different countries. The tradition of studying the scientific and historical heritage of Mirzo Ulugbek has a centuries-old history. Issues related to his life and work are reflected in the research carried out by representatives of the schools of Oriental Studies and history of Western Europe, Russia and Uzbekistan².

The first - born son of Shahruh Mirza, the fourth son of the Timurid ruler Muhammad Taragai sahibqiran Amir Temur, was born on 22 March 1394 (19th Sunday of the month before jumodul, 796 ah) in Sultonia, Iraqi Ajam. He is named Muhammad Taragai. The name was the name of Temür's late father and had not yet been given to any of the Temüri Princes. But since he is called "Ulugbek" by his grandfather with special affection, his main name remains

¹ Mirkhanova, M. A. The great scientist and statesman Mirzo Ulugbek // Young Scientist — 2016. No. 8 (112). p. 821.

² <https://www.google.uz>

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Ulugbek². Ulughbek Mirzo was raised at the court of his grandfather Amir Temur from an early age, and was influenced by the olimu fuzalos who gathered at the court and became interested in science. Ulugbek has always been near his grandfather, including when walking and receiving ambassadors. Ulugbek, like other princes, had the best teachers .

At the top of the Temüri dynasty of 1405 sits the son of Temür - Shahruh, who was elected at the residence of Herot. The administration of Movaraunnahr is handed over to Ulugbek, the eldest son of Shohruh, grandson of Amir Temur. 1409 year Ulughbek is proclaimed governor of Samarkand. Mirzo Ulugbek ascended the throne of Movarounnahr at a very young age, that is, at the age of 15, and ruled the state for 40 years. Mirzo Ulugbek was at the same time a just king, and reason-a scientist who had no equal in thought and a great personality who embodied many spiritual qualities. Mirzo Ulugbek is not very fond of military campaigns, his military campaigns were organized only to eliminate the impending danger. He was obsessed with science, occupied with urban and Rural Improvement. Mirzoulugbek establishes madrasas in Bukhara in 1417, Samarkand in 1420, and Gijduvan in 1432-1433. Ulughbek built two madrasas in Samarkand: one as part of the Registan ensemble and the other as part of the Ghor Amir ensemble. Ulughbek himself delivered weekly lectures at each of these madrasas, among other scholars .

The observatory built by Mirzo Ulugbek in Samarkand in the 15th century had a large globe. It showed climatic boundaries, and you could also see mountains, deserts, seas and rivers in it. Therefore, the second Globe in the world was created by Samarkand astronomers. According to historical sources, Ulughbek built a sundial in Samarkand with a height of 50 meters. These rare watches are also not preserved. In addition to improving the quality of education, he began to build his Samarkand Observatory. In the implementation of this huge project, he was helped in scientific activities by the colleagues of Mirzo Ulugbek. These are Rumi, Jamshid Al-Koshiy and Ali birders can be said in Kazizo. Ali Qushchi, like Ulughbek's son, was his closest disciple. They were always with Mirzo Ulugbek³.

If the above-mentioned scientists, led by Mirzo Ulugbek, conducted theoretical studies on astronomy in madrasa, in practice these studies were examined at the Observatory. The result of this and other studies is, of course, his famous main work “Zij-I jadidi Guragani”, that is, the catalog of astronomical tables of Ulugbek, which glorified the Samarkand Academy all over the world. The fact is that when Mirzo Ulugbek studied the astronomical tables of his predecessors, noticing that not all calculations were correct, he decided to recalculate the coordinates and make new more accurate tables⁴ .

³ <https://upl.uz> .

⁴ Mirza Ulugbek at the observatory and museum. <https://samarkand.uz>

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The work "Ziji Koragani" is the most famous work of Ulugbek's pen. It identifies the position and holotype of 1,018 sobita (non-excited) stars. The coordinates of 683 georgafic points located throughout the middle and Middle Eastern countries of Central Asia with respect to the latitude of Samarkand are defined. A number of rare works on mathematics and astronomy, created on the basis of the results of the research of the Ulugbek Observatory, are still gaining the attention of scientists today.

In 1941, he wrote a brochure about the Ulugbek Observatory. E. Masson wrote, " the Observatory, in which the best artistic and architectural forces were involved in the creation of the capital, was undoubtedly distinguished from other large public buildings of the time not only by its unusual forms, but also by a slightly different ratio of color combinations in the exterior decoration. At the same time, in connection with the observations of astronomers covered with a mysterious fog, it was impossible to evoke the involuntary respect of contemporaries, which was reflected in the noble or high-rise building "imati olia". His scientific work was evaluated in this way, which glorified him and Samarkand all over the world. By nature, he was a peaceful man, a patriot, a man with a high love for Science, for building. After the death of his father Shohruh, 1447 would be the head of the Timurid dynasty.

In addition to the secular sciences, history, literature and art, especially fine arts, flourished in Muvarounnahr during the time of Mirzo Ulugbek. Ulugbek's younger brother Boysunqur is also known to have engaged in mutual correspondence on topics of scientific literature. While ulughbek wanted to prove in poetry that the great Nizami Ganjavi style and School of the Azerbaijani poet was superior, Mirzo Boysunqur argued as a true product of the creativity of the great poet and thinker Amir Khusrav Dehlavi. Ulugbek knew Arabic and Persian perfectly, in addition to his native language (the chigatoy-Turkic language of that time). In his famous work "Historia Rashidi", Muhammad Haydar writes that Mirzo Ulughbek was "a historiographical sage and had also written down the history of the "four ulus"". The work was Ulugbek's "Historia arba' ulus", which reflected the political life of the countries once occupied by Genghis Khan in the 13th century – the first half of the 14th century⁵.

Mirzo Ulugbek made many scientific observations at the observatory he founded. These observations resulted in the completion of " Ziji jadidius Koragonius " in 1437. Composed in four movements, Part 2 of the work consists of 22 chapters and presents a stationary state of 1,018 stars . This work is a large scientific resource that contains very valuable information about astronomy. This work has been widely used in the science of astronomy for many centuries.

⁵ Mirzo Ulugbek hakida – buyuk alimning biography. <https://sputniknews-uz.com>

Let us briefly dwell on his copies. There are currently four abridged copies of which two are in England, one copy is in the library of the city of Bankupur, India, and a fourth copy is in the United States at Harbard University.

Mirzo Ulugbek's great discoveries in science were appreciated by many scientists, historians and expressed their warm opinion.

According to the description of the Great Alisher Navoi, Ulughbek was also an excellent poet. And the book "Tuxfatu surur" is a sign that he is a great music connoisseur. In "Muhit attafviq", Ulughbek's Bilujiy "is shown to have composed large pieces of music such as" Shadiyya "(which has come down to us)," morals"," Tabrizi"," Usuli ravon"," Usuli bahriy". According to "Muhit ut-tavorix", Ulugbek Mirzo Zari was also a musicologist in shinawan. He created musical works such as bulujiy, shoddy, moral, ulusiy and usuli Ravan, performed in large and small naqoras. Muhammad Haydar Mirzo, author of "Historia Rashidi", also describes Ulugbek Mirzo as a mature scholar, saying that "Mirzo Ulugbek was a historiographical sage and had written down the history of "Historia arba' ulus" (the four ulus)". This was also reported by historian Fiosiddin Khondamir (1475-1534).

Another great Uzbek scientist, Qori Niyazi, wrote: "the appearance of any historical person on the world arena, without any coincidence, but his creation is born on the basis of a certain heritage and a certain ground. Therefore, the floor of Ulughbek's work is not accidental". Indeed, Mirzo Ulugbek had no equal in scholarship and phosilm⁶.

In conclusion, the academy created by Mirzo Ulugbek is considered proud of its scientific activities and for today in return for the work of a number of scientists who have worked in it. A number of works created at that time are vivid evidence of our opinion that even from the point of view of today it does not lose its relevance. Therefore, great people who lived in the historical turning point are always proud of what they have done. Mirzo Ulugbek can rightfully be called the leader of the science of stars. And his outstanding contribution to the science of his time as both a ruler and a scientist lives for life in the memory of generations, and they still refer to Ulugbek's rich scientific heritage many times in their scientific work.

⁶ Come on! <https://uza.uz/uz/posts/daho-tugilgan-kun>.

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